

The author is dead, but what if they never lived? A reception experiment on Czech AI- and human-authored poetry

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Abstract

Large language models are increasingly capable of producing creative texts, yet most studies on AI-generated poetry focus on English—a language that dominates training data. In this article, we examine the perception of AI- and human-written Czech poetry. We ask if Czech native speakers are able to identify it and how they aesthetically judge it. Participants performed at chance level when guessing authorship (45.8 per cent correct on average), indicating that Czech AI-generated poems were largely indistinguishable from human-written ones. Aesthetic evaluations revealed a strong authorship bias: when participants believed a poem was AI-generated, they rated it as less favorably, even though AI poems were in fact rated equally or more favorably than human ones on average. The logistic regression model uncovered that the more the people liked a poem, the less probable was that they accurately assign the authorship. Familiarity with poetry or literary background had no effect on recognition accuracy. Our findings show that AI can convincingly produce poetry even in a morphologically complex, low-resource (with respect to the training data of AI models) Slavic language such as Czech. The results suggest that readers' beliefs about authorship and the aesthetic evaluation of the poem are interconnected.

Keywords large language models; Czech poetry; authorship; aesthetic judgments.

1. Introduction

Is authorship important to the enjoyment of art? This question is hardly new. In literary theory, the possibility of a work standing apart from its author has long been debated. A decisive impulse came from Roland Barthes in his famous essay, *The Death of the Author* (*La mort de l'auteur*, 1968). According to him, “the image of literature to be found in contemporary culture is tyrannically centered on the author, his person, his history, his tastes [...]” (Barthes 1967). To end such tyranny, Barthes proposes a radical shift toward the reader. “[H]e is only that someone who holds gathered into a single field all the paths of which the text is constituted” (Barthes 1967), so that the author must die in the reader's interest.

In practice, however, the author seems hard to kill. The difficulty of separating a work from its maker is evident, for instance, from readers boycotting best-selling writers over offensive public stances or misconduct, or in seeking out books precisely because they are written by a favorite novelist or celebrity. These examples suggest that authorship shapes how audience approach and value artworks.

Nowadays, as artificial intelligence enters the field of art, the question of authorship is primarily addressed with regard to human co-authors in the areas of ethics and law, while the centuries-long debate over authorship in literary theory seems to be overlooked.¹ But if it holds that the author is dead, does it matter that they never lived? If the reader is the one to play the key role in

Figure 7. Average making sense according to poem authorship.

Figure 8. Average making sense according to perceived poem authorship.

generated poems are evaluated similarly to those written by humans, or AI tends to score higher.

We emphasize that the direction of this correlation cannot be determined from our data: people either think about a poem that it is authored by AI and, therefore, like it less, or they do not like a poem very much and, therefore, think it is authored by AI. Both processes may operate simultaneously, and they may differ across individuals.

In the next section, we will focus on the scales in more detail with respect to the differences between modern and nonsense poetry.

5.3 Can AI mimic nonsense features?

To assess whether AI can mimic nonsense poetry and its specific features, we employed bootstrapped confidence intervals. In this analysis, we compared rating profiles across four conditions: modern poems written by AI, modern

poems written by humans, nonsense poems written by AI, and nonsense poems written by humans. By that, we can compare the ratings of AI nonsense poetry with both nonsense human poetry (expected to be rated similarly) and modern AI poetry (expected to be rated lower on the scales indicating nonsense poetry). Additionally, it is important to determine whether human-written nonsense poetry is perceived differently from modern human-written poetry, therefore, whether the theoretical attributes of nonsense poetry are even perceived by people.

In the rating scales, we used these attributes: nonsense poetry is described as playful (*hravá*) and imaginative (*nápaditá*), therefore, these categories should be rated higher on the scales for nonsense poetry compared to modern. On the other hand, nonsense poetry should not make sense (*smysluplná*) and is not serious (*vážná*), therefore, we expect these scales to be rated lower for nonsense poetry compared to modern poetry.

Figure 12. Average serious according to poem authorship.

poetry, and (2) AI consistently mimics the attributes of nonsense poetry and often even exaggerates these attributes in comparison to human nonsense poetry.

Lastly, we asked how well the poems rhyme. This aspect was more objective and less evaluative, as we aimed to examine whether AI can produce rhyming poetry in Czech. As shown in Fig. 13, when human-authored nonsense poems

contained rhyme, AI was able to successfully mimic this pattern, with comparable ratings ($M = 1.54$, 95% CI [1.48, 1.60] for AI; $M = 1.53$, 95% CI [1.46, 1.59] for human). Additionally, while Czech modern poems written by humans were mostly non-rhyming ($M = 0.31$, 95% CI [0.26, 0.37]), AI incorporated rhyme into modern poems as well, although to a lesser extent than in nonsense poems ($M = 1.08$, 95% CI [1.00, 1.16]).

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